

**Managerial competency requirements that enhance organisational competences: a study
of a Sri Lankan telecom organisation**

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The study aims to differentiate firm-level capabilities in terms of managerial-level competencies of a Sri Lankan telecommunication service provider. A framework is developed and survey data is used to identify a range of factors at managerial competency level that form firm-level capabilities as a result. Multiple regression is used to identify how much variance in the latter is predicted by the former. It is expected that the methodology adopted in identifying and integrating managerial-level competencies and firm-level capabilities provides an innovative integrated methodology of significant value for practitioners and academics alike. Managerial implications, limitations and directions for future research are discussed.

Key words: job-competencies; managerial competencies; firm-level capabilities; strategic human resource management; Sri Lanka

Introduction

The competencies comprise of both personal competencies (job-competency level) and organisational competences (firm-level capabilities) (Boam and Sparrow, 1992; Dunphy et al., 1997; Sparrow, 1994). Boam and Sparrow (1992) and Sparrow (1994) argue that competency identification systems need to identify both personal competencies and organisational competences. Personal competencies are those possessed by an individual in terms of experience, technical knowledge, skills and abilities that are causally related to effective or superior performance in a job (Boyatzis, 1982). Organisational competences, on the other hand, consist of a combination of differentiated skills, complimentary assets, and routines that provide the basis for a firm's competitive capacities and sustainable advantage in a particular business. These are embedded in the organisational processes and systems and absorbed by all its members and structures (Escrig-Tena and Bou-Llugar, 2005; Murray and Donegan, 2003). Extant literature describes the interdependence between individual-level competencies and firm-level capabilities, where individual-level is linked to firm-level, which in turn sustain organisational strategy (Bhattacharya et al., 2005; De Carolis, 2003; Levenson et al., 2006; Lustri et al., 2007). This is to a large extent driven by business and

human resources agenda to deliver business performance, where improvements in the performance of individuals are seen as a key in the process (Engle et al., 2001; Godbout, 2000; Harvey et al., 2000; Kochanski and Ruse, 1996; Losey, 1998).

The competency-based approach puts the human being at the centre of attention and underlines the importance of human resources to reach the objectives of the organisation (Hondegheem and Vandermeulen, 2000). Vertically, competency framework is a tool to delineate job-level competencies and firm-level capabilities from the mission and strategy of the organisation. Horizontally, competency framework can be used for different purposes in human resource management (HRM), such as selection, appraisal, development and reward (Becker et al., 2001; Hondegheem and Vandermeulen, 2000; Schippmann et al., 2000; Sparrow, 1995). This echoes comments made by Woodruffe (1993) that competencies should be the common language of the HRM system which enable an organisation to match its human resources against the resources it needs. Therefore, a competency-based approach, on one hand, guides to identify competency requirements of current and future human resource needs in alignment with organisational strategies, and on the other hand, focuses on individual and team development plans to eliminate competency gaps in terms of those requested by a project, job role, or enterprise strategy (Draganidis and Mentzas, 2006). In this regard, a key integrative concept is that of occupational competence, especially managerial competence. The underlying thrust has been the recognition that organisational effectiveness is in part related to the performance of managers, a conception given some support by the research conducted by Boyatzis (1982).

Therefore, there is a need to integrate managerial-level competencies with firm-level capabilities (Kochanski and Ruse, 1996; Losey, 1998; Lustri et al., 2007). However, empirical research in this area is limited. For instance, Hondegheem and Vandermeulen (2000) argued that although there are some attempts to derive managerial competencies from organisational strategies, this area is not yet fully developed. This emphasises the need of identifying competency gaps of managerial employees in terms of an organisation's specific business strategies (see Athey and Orth, 1999; Homer, 2001; King, 2001; Soosay,

2005; Wright et al., 2001; Yang et al., 2006). Therefore, empirical research studies are needed to address the relationship between managerial-level competencies and firm-level capabilities to understand specific, meaningful job-related competencies which are related to the strategic needs of the business in a contingent context.

In the above context, this study aims to differentiate firm-level capabilities in terms of managerial-level competencies of a Sri Lankan telecommunication service provider. It is expected that the methodology adopted in identifying and integrating managerial-level competencies and firm-level capabilities provides an innovative integrated methodology of significant value for practitioners and academics alike. Consequently, it will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. Consistent with the objectives, the next section discusses the theoretical background. This is followed by the explanation of research design and methodologies employed. The subsequent section discusses the main findings. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings.

Theoretical background

Competency and competence

The term “competency” was first used in the managerial context in the research conducted by Boyatzis (1982) to identify the characteristics which distinguish superior from average managerial performance. Boyatzis adopted the term “competency”, plural “competencies” to describe an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally related to effective or superior performance in a job (Boyatzis, 1982). The study concluded that there is no single factor but a range of factors that differentiated superior from average performers. These included personal characteristics, experience, motives, and other attributes. Since then the literature on competency is characterised by a huge diversity of definitions. For the study purposes, there is a need to distinguish between "competence" and "competency". The term "competence" is used to refer to the standard of performance reached while "competency" is used to refer to the behaviour by which it is achieved. In other words, one describes what people can do while the other focuses on how they do it. The plural of each word, therefore,

gives two different meanings. Competences refer to the range of skills which are satisfactorily performed while competencies refer to the behaviours adopted in competent performance (see Rowe, 1995). There is, therefore, an interface between the two, i.e. the competent application of a competency is likely to make one act in a competent manner, and vice versa.

In the above context, individual competencies can be defined as an input or an output of human behaviour. When competencies are viewed as outputs, employees display competencies in the degree to which their work meets or exceeds prescribed work standards. When competencies are seen as inputs, they consist of clusters of knowledge, attitudes and skills that affect an individual's ability to perform (see Heffernan and Flood 2000; Stuart and Lindsay 1997). By competency in this study is meant input measures in the manner suggested by Boyatzis (1982) and Spencer and Spencer (1993) rather than outputs. As the findings of this study could have individual development focus, the definition given by Hay Group (2001) was used, i.e., competency is a measurable characteristic of a person that is related to effective performance in a specific job, organisation or culture. These characteristics are defined in terms of behaviours. Because competencies are behavioural, they can be developed.

With regard to firm-level capabilities, organisational competences are seen as a combination of skills and knowledge that belong to the organisation itself that relate to a particular organisation's strategic performance (Dunphy et al., 1997; Escrig-Tena and Bou-Llugar, 2005; Murray and Donegan, 2003). Specifically, Bogner and Thomas (1994) defined organisational competences as the abilities and specific skills that a firm possesses in the deployment of its resources and its cognitive characteristics, which are geared towards the accomplishment of activities that permit the attainment of certain objectives (Bogner and Thomas, 1994, p. 113). In a similar vein, Sanchez et al. (1996, p. 8) indicate three conditions that a competency must meet as: it must have an organisational component in the sense of the coordination and deployment of assets; it must have an intention component as it must imply certain premeditated activities to sustain the coordinated deployment of assets; and it

must have a goal attainment component as the coordination of assets must help a firm achieve its goals. This operationalisation of firm-level capabilities was also adopted by Escrig-Tena and Bou-Llusar (2005).

The relationship between managerial competencies and organisational competences

The purpose of conducting this study is to differentiate organisational-level capabilities in terms of managerial-level competencies. Therefore, the ideal scenario is to identify specific, meaningful job-related competencies which are also related to strategic needs of a business. There are two ways to achieve this. The first approach, top-down stream of thinking, is to consider organisational competences as independent variables and managerial competencies as dependent variables. The second approach, bottom-up stream of thinking, is to consider managerial competencies as independent variables and organisational competences as dependent variables (Peteraf, 1993; Yang et al., 2006). Both these approaches ensure that managerial competencies remain related to strategic priorities of the business. Between the two, bottom-up approach indicates that strategic processes were initiated by an examination of a firm's existing capabilities that serve as comparative advantages to win the competitive edge (Yang et al., 2006). This debate on how to treat organisational competences and management competencies within management literature came side by side with the advent of the resource-based view of the firm amongst the strategists (e.g. Prahalad and Hamel, 1990, 1993) and amongst the HRM theorists (e.g. Boam and Sparrow, 1992). The human *resources* view tended to treat individuals as a contingency to be fitted to strategy whereas the *resourceful* humans view argued that the stock of human resources in itself opened up the way to better strategic thought and execution. For this study, bottom-up approach was adopted to differentiate organisational competences in terms of management competencies.

In the above context, to achieve superior organisational performance, it is important to identify which particular set of managerial competencies are required for a business to achieve its strategic goals. Equally vital is the ability to “health-check” those competencies

on a regular basis (Homer, 2001). Although there is, and always has been, a considerable debate within the HRM field about the best ways to identify competency requirements (Boam and Sparrow, 1992; Sparrow, 2002), management literature proposes three sources to derive competency requirements (refer to Agut et al 2003). These are the business as reflected in strategic areas of competence; the job itself, in terms of business and professional/technical requirements and in terms of personal and managerial competencies; the organisation in terms of culture and the level at which an individual operates (Agut et al 2003). Therefore, it is essential to clarify the critical success factors for a business strategy, so that the areas of strategic competence can be identified (Tovey, 2006). A strategic area of competence is defined as an area in which an organisation must be competent, if it is to succeed in its mission, and which has implications for managerial competencies (Tovey, 1994). Therefore, for an organisation to succeed, it is necessary for it to possess capabilities in each strategic area of competence. At the organisational level, competence gaps could be identified as the difference between competence requirements and the extent to which those are possessed by the organisation. Therefore, such a competence deficit could be operationalised as the gap between the current and required level of a competence. Though such a perceived gap could often be an expression of preference, such a competence deficit could be useful in making organisational strategic decisions.

From the management development viewpoint, it is important to know whether a manager possesses the required competencies to achieve an expert job performance. This could be identified by exploring the possible competency gaps (Agut et al., 2003). A discrepancy or a gap arises when a competency an individual possesses is lower than what is required for an effective performance (Agut and Grau, 2002; Boydell and Leary, 1996; Moore and Dutton, 1978). Such a deficit could be solved through training or other interventions, such as job enrichment, job content innovation, job redesign, or enhancement of the organisational climate (Brownell and Goldsmith, 2006; Le Deist and Winterton, 2005). When competency needs are considered in terms of gaps, it allows for a better understanding of efficient managerial performance on the job (Agut et al., 2003; Barber and

Tietje, 2004). Collin (1989) and Antonacopoulou and FitzGerald (1996) argued that although one of the aims of competency development is to ensure that managers will be competent to perform effectively in the future, competency studies tend to focus on what managers do now. Antonacopoulou and FitzGerald (1996) suggest that in rapidly changing work environments, there is a danger that competency approach may encourage organisations developing competencies of the past rather than developing dynamic, flexible and adaptable managers capable of facing the challenges of tomorrow. Hence, competencies should reflect an organisation's current and future needs (Pickett, 1998; Prahalad and Hamel, 1990). Therefore, for the study, a competency deficit or competency need is operationalised as the gap between the current and required level of a competency for efficient job performance.

Research design and methodology

Case description

The study is confined to a fully integrated telecommunication service provider, identified as Company X. It has become the leading company in the industry in Sri Lanka. Currently, Company X serves over 1.2 million corporate and residential customers in Sri Lanka with more than one million exchange lines as well as provides network solutions to other licensed operators. With regard to strategic directions of the company, during the period of 1997-2006, four strategic directions have been followed. From 1997 to 1999, the emphasis was on the expansion of network capacity resulting in an accelerated increase in the customer base. From 2000 to 2001, the emphasis was on customer satisfaction and quality of service. From 2002-2003, the emphasis was on structural strengthening to meet competition. Regional and global connectivity and revenue diversification were the strategies during the period of 2004-2006. According to the monthly human resource report as of July 2006, Company X has more than 6000 employees in total. Specifically, there were 541 managerial level employees, 1026 middle level technical employees, 1279 clerical and aligned employees, 605 call centre employees, 2232 technical employees, 358 non-technical employees, and 290 drivers as permanent staff. Of the total employees (6331), 2484 were attached to

headquarters while 3847 were attached to regional offices island-wide. The average age of the employees is 42.

The 541 managerial level employees of Company X were considered as the population of the study. Of the 541 managerial employees, 510 were contactable during September 2006 when the survey was conducted; some were not contactable as they had left for either official foreign assignments or were on leave. The questionnaire was distributed through email or printed form. The questionnaire was voluntarily completed and returned by 203 subjects within 4 weeks of the initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 198 usable responses resulted in 39% response rate. Of the respondents, 70% were males and 30% were females. The mean age was 40 years; 85% were married while 15% were single. Of the sample, 85% reported having a Bachelor's degree or postgraduate level university education. The average job tenure in Company X was 13 years while the average job tenure in Company X in the current field of specialisation was 7 years. On average, there were nine subordinates directly reporting each respondent. The final sample covered all the fields of employment as shown in Table 1.

Insert Table 1 about here

Measures

To achieve the purpose of the study, the identification of relevant managerial competencies is the foundation. In generating the list of managerial competencies to be considered for the study, the methodologies adopted by recent competency research were studied (such as Barber and Tietje, 2004; Escrig-Tena and Bou-Llusar, 2005; Dunphy et al., 1997; Murray and Donegan, 2003; Robinson et al., 2005, 2007; Tovey, 1994; Walsh and Linton, 2001; Yang et al., 2006). For instance, Murray and Donegan (2003) delineated competencies drawing from several previous studies. Escrig-Tena and Bou-Llusar (2005) and Barber and Tietje (2004) developed their own list of competencies by first deriving from literature and

then verifying the suitability by consulting a group of experts. Hence, literature on the generation of list of competencies reveals that some build their lists drawing from previous research while some others have developed their own lists following a certain procedure.

For the current study, five-step methodology was used to identify competencies that define a successful manager within the telecommunication industry as perceived by industry experts and managers in Sri Lanka. First, a comprehensive list of competencies was created that were taken from competency literature. Second, in order to standardise the terminology of competency items, a list of 107 technical and generic competencies was summarised – they had been abstracted from various sources in literature. This list was considered as the hypothesised list of competencies. As the third step, a panel of industry experts from the telecommunication industry was consulted to rank the importance of each competency for managers in the telecommunication industry from the hypothesised competency list created. As the fourth step, a randomly selected team of managers from the telecommunication industry was consulted to rank the importance of each competency for managers in the telecommunication industry from the hypothesised competency list created. It was decided to take the competencies that are consistently rated of great importance by the two panels. Therefore, as the fifth and final step, the initial lists along with the ranks given by the two panels were independently analysed by us to identify the most important competencies and to eliminate duplicates (also see Wickramasinghe and De Zoyza, 2009). A similar process was also used by Robinson et al. (2007) to forecast future competency requirements in their study. The final list comprised of 31 managerial competencies and reflected the absolute minimum number of areas in which capabilities are required for effective and superior performance in a job. The same five step procedure was deployed to yield the list of 30 organisational competences. Assuming that 31 managerial competencies would predict 30 organisational competences, conceptual model shown in Figure 1 is developed for the study.

Take in Figure 1

In the study, competency gaps were identified as the difference between perceived future requirements and the extent to which these are currently possessed at both managerial-level and organisational-level. The self-evaluation method of personal competencies was used in the research (see Agut et al., 2003; Hansson, 2001; Kersh and Evans, 2005; Robinson et al., 2007; Tovey, 1994). Five point Likert scale was used to establish the level of current competency expertise and level of competency requirements for future success at both managerial and organisational level. The managerial competency levels were established as follows:

- Current competency expertise level: The five point Likert scale used to establish the level of competencies currently possessed is: 5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=Nothing at all. In the current expertise, a respondent estimates his or her competency on each of the 31 competencies.
- Competency requirements for future success: The five point Likert scale used to establish the level of competency importance for future success is: 5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=No Need. In future requirement, a respondent makes a judgment on how important each of the 31 competencies will be for the future job performance (three years to the future).

In establishing organisational competence levels the same procedure was followed. Respondents were instructed to focus on those competences that they feel currently possessed by and required for future success of Company X.

The size of the competency gap was established by measuring the difference between the level of competency currently possessed and level of competency requirement for future success (see Agut et al., 2003; Tovey, 1994). The gaps were calculated for each respondent for each competency item. Following the criterion proposed by Agut and Grau (2002), three types of competency gaps were identified: negative gap (the present competency level is lower than that required: value \leq -.51); adjustment margin (the present

competency level is lower but close to that required: $-.5 \leq \text{value} \leq .5$); and positive gap (the present competency level is higher than that required: $\text{value} \geq .51$). Though three different situations could be obtained from the subtraction, in this study focus is on negative gaps and adjustment margin, since those are the needs. In establishing organisational competence gaps the same procedure was followed.

The list of 31 managerial competencies rating both current expertise and future importance of each competency and list of 30 organisational competences rating both current expertise and future importance of each competency were incorporated into the self-administered survey questionnaire for pre-testing. The pre-tested survey questionnaire was administered among the selected respondents as detailed in the section on case description. It should be noted that participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous.

Methods of data analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to analyse scores and to derive gaps at the managerial level as well as organisational level. Paired sample t-test was performed to explore differences between the current expertise level and future importance level in order to identify the most needed competencies. One-way ANOVA was used to explore whether there are any differences in perceived competency levels by the field of specialisation.

In the attempt to identify underlying dimensions as perceived by respondents, 31 managerial competencies and 30 organisational competences were subjected to factor analysis. In the study, factor analysis was used as a form of data reduction, not theoretical specification. For this, principal components factor analysis was performed for managerial competencies and organisational competences, separately with direct oblimin rotation (suppressed absolute values less than 0.50). The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and

overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2006). Total of five “managerial competency clusters” and four “organisational competency clusters” emerged. The final solutions are summarised in Table 4 and Table 5, which contains factor loadings, factor variance percentages and Cronbach’s alpha of the factor. After revealing the components (clusters), the component scores were calculated for each competency cluster. These aggregation statistics established higher-order variables (for each competency cluster) to be used in the subsequent analysis, namely, correlation and regression. Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to identify relationships across managerial clusters and organisational clusters. To determine how five managerial clusters predict four organisational clusters, a total of four multiple regression runs were performed.

Results

The results of the managerial competency needs are summarised in Table 2. The competency gaps range between -.95 and -.35. The results of the t-test are also shown in Table 2.

Insert Table 2 about here

The results of the organisational competency needs are summarised in Table 3. The competence gaps range between -1.74 and -.65. The results of the t-test are also shown in Table 3.

Insert Table 3 about here

The results of the principal components factor analysis for managerial competencies are summarised in Table 4. The managerial competencies were made up of five clusters. Cluster 1 was labelled as “transformational and responsiveness management”, cluster 2 as

“foundational systems”, cluster 3 as “proactivity”, cluster 4 as “functional efficacy” and cluster 5 as “technical writing”.

Insert Table 4 about here

The results of the principal components factor analysis for organisational competences are summarised in Table 5. The organisational competences are made up of four clusters. Cluster 1 was labelled as “responsiveness planning”, cluster 2 as “market responsiveness”, cluster 3 as “technical foundations” and cluster 4 as “integrated supply chain and firm performance”.

Insert Table 5 about here

Table 6 shows the differences in competency levels by the field of specialisation. The correlations between competency clusters are shown in Table 7.

Insert Table 6 about here

Insert Table 7 about here

Table 8 summarises the results of multiple regression showing the proportion of the variance in organisational competency clusters explained by managerial competency clusters. As shown in Table 8, for instance, managerial competency clusters “proactivity” and “transformational and responsiveness management” are significant in explaining the

organisational competency cluster “market responsiveness”. Figure 2 shows the results figuratively.

Insert Table 8 about here

Take in Figure 2

Discussion and managerial implications

The study aimed to differentiate organisational-level capabilities in terms of managerial-level competencies. It used survey data collected from 198 managerial level employees from a Sri Lankan telecommunication service provider to identify a range of factors at job-competency and organisational-capability levels. Subsequently, multiple regression was used to identify how much variance in the latter is predicted by the former.

Though there are several means that could be used to derive competency requirements by taking into account an individual’s perception of how important a specific competency for performing a particular job could avoid an unbalanced focus on less important competencies (see Graham and Tarbell, 2006; Hansson, 2001; Kersh and Evans, 2005). Therefore, self-reporting method was used to assess competency levels in this study as it plays an increasingly prominent role in education and training and development field (see Agut et al., 2003; Hayes et al., 2000). When self-reports reflect an individual’s levels of competency, an aggregation of these perceptions is possible. This method of aggregation of individual perceptions of the levels of competency gives possibilities to apply strategic management decisions based upon the model developed. The responses led to identify managerial as well as organisational competency gaps as the perceived difference between requirements and the extent to which these are possessed.

The study led to the identification of specific competencies required by individual managers that would construct the foundation to operationalise behaviours and capabilities needed for the achievement of firm-level capabilities. This was in accordance with the research framework developed for the study. Few empirical studies have tried to differentiate firm-level capabilities in terms of different elements of managerial-level competencies. In this context, the study attempted to provide a “rough blueprint” for the fostering of much needed additional research in the domain of the exploration of operational linkages and indicators between managerial competencies and organisational competences. The findings of this study could be used as a “benchmark” and source of general guidance in stimulating much needed research stream. Therefore, from a theoretical viewpoint, this study makes a contribution to the analysis of managerial-level competencies and firm-level capabilities based on a competency framework.

The judicious management of competencies shows an orientation towards the future and horizontal and vertical integration of HRM. The competency framework developed in the study helps to align the HRM system vertically with the organisation's strategic objectives. In the study competencies were addressed at two different, but interrelated levels- the managerial level and the organisational level- as it is accepted that organisations that successfully integrate strategic thinking at these two levels will form the basis of an enduring competitive advantage (see Soosay, 2005). The competency framework developed in the study also helps to align the HRM system horizontally with other HRM functions, where the results of the study provide a tool for selection, training and development, performance management and management of careers.

The findings of the study have several implications. To achieve the expected results from the framework developed in the study, the starting-point is the identification of strategic competences (from a set of managerial competencies) that would be the most important for the organisation's competitive and strategic success. Therefore, first organisations must create a competency model through a systematic process of data collection, at managerial and organisational levels. Second, an operational definition for each competency and sub-

competency has to be developed, together with measurable or observable performance indicators or standards against which to evaluate. Third, because the outcome serves as the foundation for making vital HRM decisions, it must be ensured that the competencies required of individuals are valid and useful. However, the study relied on individuals' self-assessment. It could be assumed that some individuals could consistently give higher (or lower) estimates of the importance of the items as well as higher (or lower) estimates of their own competency. It could further assume that not all competencies are judged equally important for performing a specific job. In this regard, the validation of competencies becomes vital because competencies describe normative behaviours, behaviours the organisation wishes to promote and develop to enhance organisational effectiveness. Fourth, the study proposed an operative method to analyse managerial competency needs in terms of gaps. Therefore, once the competency deficits are detected, those could be solved using an appropriate method. However, the organisation has to decide which competencies have to be solved and how. In this regard identifying the most needed competencies through the highest gaps makes sense. Fifth, having diagnosed the most important competencies, it is then necessary to target and develop them continuously (internally) and improvements must be measured. This implies the need of having performance measurement systems which are as objective and robust as possible. However, a number of business pressures and uncertainty create the need for new competencies in the organisation. This makes it to develop or acquire these newly identified competencies.

When considering the possible strategies- training or other strategies- available to address competency needs of individuals, competency literature well recognises the importance of ensuring that managerial training plans are linked to business goals, and illustrate how a competency management system can help an organisation to improve the effectiveness of its training. In this regard, the gap analysis method of the identification of competency needs involves matching the needs to training interventions. Such a link between competencies and training interventions add value to users and they could see what training is needed in order to develop required competences.

The competency framework presented has implications for the role of line managers and HRM function. Line managers engage in selection, assessment, development and succession of managerial employees under his or her supervision. All these four activities are influenced by competencies. Selection relies on clear definitions of competencies, which must be derived from the strategic requirements at the organisational level. Performance assessment has to be dealt with at the levels of current job performance and potential. It also impacts on developing individuals for current job performance as well as for the succession to future positions. Thus, the findings imply the role that line managers has to play to ensure that managerial competency requirements remain strategically focused. This further implies the need of sharing of the responsibility with HR managers. Furthermore, the competency framework suggests that organisations have to redefine the HRM function and to rethink their expectations of it. HR managers have to evaluate the competencies on a regular basis. This suggests the need of HRM function to become strategic and flexible and be prepared to support organisational changes.

Limitations and suggestions for further research

The study has some limitations. For the study purposes competencies were defined simply, as a headline plus a few sample behaviours, so competency definitions used do not cater for multiple levels of detail and mastery. However, the way competencies will be defined will depend on how competencies will be used and the purpose of the study. We have gone through a rigorous process in trying to winnow the long list of terms and definitions extant in the literature to an industry specific list. However, in future studies Delphi method could be used to derive competency lists. The organisational competences were identified by the managerial level employees based on their perception of how well the organisation overall possessed each of the 30 competences and how important each of the 30 competences for the organisation in the future. However, one could argue that managerial employees working in different functional areas of the company do not have a common frame for viewing the organisation's future. Therefore, future studies could overcome this limitation by employing

multiple sources of data that could assist in confirming, enriching, or questioning managerial perceptions. In the current study, the levels of competency is measured only by using managers' self-assessment. Though previous studies had shown that managers are reliable and valid informants, it could be argued that individuals do not always know exactly what competencies they lack, and that could flaw the needs identified. Therefore, future studies could overcome this limitation by using techniques to improve rater accuracy, such as standardisation, or incorporating perceptions of subordinates, superiors and industry experts.

To provide readers with some sense of derived competency clusters through the factor analysis, we labelled them. In doing so, we attempted to label them as appropriately as possible to describe the content included in the each competency cluster. However, one could propose different labels than what we have proposed. Further, it should be noted that factors analysis was used as a form of data reduction. The factors derived are context-specific and could not be generalised to other organisations. Therefore, a repeat of this study in the same firm or in another firm would likely result in different loadings and different exploratory factors.

Of the 510 managers contacted for the survey, only 198 voluntarily responded to the survey. Some could see this low response rate as problematic given the attempt to link individual competencies to firm-level capabilities. However, to increase the response rate, we designed the survey questionnaire in such a way for them to allow responding to the survey questionnaire anonymously. However, literature identifies non-response as a problem if non-respondents are a non-random sample of the total sample. To explain non-response bias, demographic characteristics of non-respondents have been investigated by many researchers. However, as we received the completed questionnaires anonymous, we were unable to compare characteristics of the respondents and non-respondents.

The study was confined to one organisation. A cross sectional study could compare the differences at various levels of management across the organisation while a longitudinal

study could provide an in-depth understanding of whether improved competencies predict improved managerial job performance and improved organisational performance.

Finally, managers' perceptions of competencies could be influenced by their cultural orientations. Therefore, it would be possible that Sri Lankan managers see different competencies as important (at both individual and organisational level) than do managers in other parts of the world. Though such comparisons would be interesting, it is beyond the scope of this study. These all open the door for further investigations.

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Tables and Figures

Tables

Table 1. Population and sample

Field of specialisation	Population		Sample		% represented in the sample
	N	%	N	%	
Finance	38	7	17	9	45
IT	32	6.5	12	6	38
Marketing	86	17	28	14	33
HR & Administration	76	15	28	14	37
Legal	10	2	7	4	70
Planning & Corporate Strategy	33	6.5	18	9	55
Operations	235	46	88	44	37
Total	510	100	198	100	39

Table 2. Managerial-level: current expertise, future importance, gaps and t-test results

	Current expertise	Future importance	Perceived gap	Type of gap	t-test (2-tailed)		
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		t	df	Sig.
Customer relations knowledge	3.88 (.81)	4.62 (.72)	-.75 (.86)	N	-11.99	189	.000
Cost consciousness	3.82 (.91)	4.49 (.75)	-.65 (.94)	N	-9.59	187	.000
Change handling skills	3.84 (.78)	4.55 (.74)	-.71 (.87)	N	-11.21	187	.000
Planning and scheduling	4.02 (.77)	4.61 (.66)	-.60 (.82)	N	-10.00	185	.000
Strategising ability	3.76 (.77)	4.51 (.76)	-.74 (.98)	N	-10.30	185	.000
Technical competence	3.75 (.82)	4.68 (.64)	-.95 (.95)	N	-13.52	182	.000
Technology application skills	3.67 (.78)	4.55 (.82)	-.87 (.93)	N	-12.92	188	.000
Safety focus	3.86 (.85)	4.41 (.82)	-.54 (.91)	N	-8.22	189	.000
Empathy with people	4.09 (.80)	4.36 (.80)	-.27 (.97)	AM	-3.82	185	.000
Conflict resolution	3.73 (.84)	4.34 (.74)	-.59 (.97)	N	-8.24	185	.000
Negotiation	3.94 (.80)	4.56 (.75)	-.60 (.93)	N	-8.85	187	.000
Empowerment ability	3.91 (.81)	4.45 (.82)	-.54 (1.02)	N	-7.29	187	.000
Holistic	3.79 (.84)	4.45 (.82)	-.66 (.95)	N	-9.49	183	.000
Creativity	3.77 (.79)	4.58 (.68)	-.82 (.90)	N	-12.33	185	.000
Coaching ability	3.78 (.93)	4.41 (.82)	-.61 (1.02)	N	-8.21	183	.000
Time management ability	3.88 (.79)	4.61 (.78)	-.72 (1.02)	N	-9.67	186	.000
Pressure management skills	3.75 (.76)	4.50 (.72)	-.73 (1.01)	N	-9.91	185	.000
Learning	3.94 (.81)	4.59 (.75)	-.63 (.96)	N	-9.00	187	.000
Listening	4.10 (.86)	4.46 (.74)	-.35 (.97)	AM	-5.01	188	.000
Oral communication	3.90 (.78)	4.54 (.73)	-.63 (.92)	N	-9.45	189	.000
Written communication	3.97 (.75)	4.59 (.66)	-.58 (.84)	N	-9.50	184	.000
Quality focus	3.94 (.70)	4.65 (.61)	-.71 (.83)	N	-11.69	188	.000
Flexibility	4.18 (.85)	4.59 (.70)	-.38 (.93)	AM	-5.70	188	.000
Team player	4.19 (.77)	4.62 (.72)	-.42 (.85)	AM	-6.92	188	.000
Customer focus	3.89 (.86)	4.56 (.79)	-.71 (.83)	N	-11.69	188	.000
Resiliency	3.98 (.80)	4.59 (.64)	-.58 (.89)	N	-8.97	184	.000
Ethical	4.03 (.80)	4.47 (.85)	-.42 (.99)	AM	-5.85	186	.000
Achievement orientation	3.90 (.83)	4.64 (.62)	-.74 (.80)	N	-12.68	186	.000
Risk taking	3.79 (.83)	4.39 (.84)	-.61 (.99)	N	-8.51	188	.000
Positive vision	4.07 (.84)	4.54 (.71)	-.42 (.96)	AM	-6.38	185	.000
Attitude to meet targets	4.28 (.75)	4.71 (.57)	-.42 (.77)	AM	-7.45	186	.000

Note: Type of gap: Value \leq -.51: negative gap (N), $-.5 \leq$ Value \leq .5: adjustment margin (AM), Value \geq .51: positive gap (P)

Table 3. Organisational-level: current expertise, future importance, gaps and t-test results

	Current expertise	Future importance	Perceived gap	Type of gap	t-test (2-tailed)		
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		t	df	Sig.
Brand equity	3.67 (.87)	4.75 (.57)	-1.09 (.96)	N	-15.50	185	.000
Close external relationship	3.41 (.80)	4.59 (.67)	-1.19 (.90)	N	-18.13	186	.000
Collaborating partners in supply chain	3.28 (.80)	4.47 (.71)	-1.19 (.92)	N	-17.39	180	.000
Organisational flexibility	3.20 (.94)	4.67 (.57)	-1.50 (1.08)	N	-18.79	183	.000
Corporate social responsibility	3.51 (.93)	4.45 (.67)	-.94 (1.05)	N	-12.12	183	.000
Customer delight	3.07 (.91)	4.79 (.54)	-1.74 (1.07)	N	-22.07	183	.000
Pricing tactics	3.03 (.91)	4.56 (.74)	-1.5 (1.09)	N	-19.34	182	.000
Enhancing performance	3.34 (.83)	4.71 (.52)	-1.38 (.92)	N	-20.45	184	.000
Ethics and integrity	3.28 (.91)	4.63 (.64)	-1.3 (1.09)	N	-16.69	182	.000
People strategy	3.13 (.91)	4.68 (.57)	-1.5 (1.04)	N	-20.09	122	.000
Financial stability	4.07 (.75)	4.73 (.53)	-.65 (.73)	N	-11.98	183	.000
Global presence	3.46 (.85)	4.60 (.66)	-1.15 (.88)	N	-17.79	183	.000
Human capital	3.71 (.79)	4.70 (.52)	-.99 (.82)	N	-16.18	180	.000
Innovation	3.25 (.90)	4.67 (.63)	-1.44 (1.04)	N	-18.71	183	.000
Integrating internal operations	3.04 (.93)	4.62 (.57)	-1.5 (1.07)	N	-20.21	185	.000
Managing change	3.28 (.81)	4.60 (.61)	-1.33 (1.00)	N	-17.96	180	.000
Marketing communication	3.14 (.91)	4.68 (.65)	-1.56 (1.06)	N	-20.00	184	.000
Organisational communication	3.14 (.88)	4.71 (.55)	-1.58 (.99)	N	-21.60	184	.000
Organisational decision making	3.07 (.93)	4.74 (.60)	-1.69 (1.11)	N	-20.61	184	.000
People development	3.21 (.86)	4.69 (.61)	-1.48 (.98)	N	-20.54	184	.000
Positioning in customers mindset	3.32 (.85)	4.74 (.63)	-1.44 (.96)	N	-20.09	179	.000
Market segmentation	3.21 (.88)	4.73 (.67)	-1.56 (1.08)	N	-19.61	182	.000
Product design	3.23 (.90)	4.70 (.64)	-1.48 (.97)	N	-20.43	179	.000
Customer orientation	3.13 (.81)	4.69 (.70)	-1.60 (1.00)	N	-21.47	180	.000
Quality of work life	3.24 (.85)	4.58 (.67)	-1.37 (1.04)	N	-17.75	182	.000
Reliable systems	3.41 (.76)	4.67 (.65)	-1.29 (.95)	N	-18.04	178	.000
Service access	3.48 (.78)	4.69 (.58)	-1.23 (.90)	N	-18.26	180	.000
Strategic location	3.53 (.84)	4.62 (.65)	-1.08 (.97)	N	-15.05	179	.000
Targeting different market segments	3.14 (.86)	4.71 (.62)	-1.59 (.98)	N	-21.93	181	.000
Technological know-how	3.86 (.73)	4.76 (.61)	-.90 (.78)	N	-15.45	180	.000

Note: Type of gap: Value \leq -.51: negative gap (N), $-.5 \leq$ Value \leq .5: adjustment margin (AM), Value \geq .51: positive gap (P).

Table 4. Factor analysis: managerial-level

	Managerial Competency Clusters				
	Transformational and responsiveness management	Foundational systems	Proactivity	Functional efficacy	Technical writing
Negotiation	.558				
Listening	.766				
Oral communication	.602				
Flexibility	.581				
Positive vision	.534				
Cost consciousness		.571			
Change handling skills		.662			
Empathy with people		.630			
Empowerment ability		.608			
Holistic		.618			
Customer focus		.511			
Achievement orientation		.501			
Attitude to meet targets		.609			
Strategising ability			.532		
Quality focus			.623		
Resiliency			.648		
Risk taking			.707		
Technical competence				.704	
Technology application skills				.665	
Safety focus				.602	
Creativity				.563	
Ethical				.624	
Written communication					.815
Explained variation	15.11	14.51	13.07	11.09	7.71
Standardised Cronbach's Alpha	.809	.885	.806	.785	-

Table 5. Factor analysis: organisational-level

	Organisational Competency Clusters			
	Responsiveness planning	Market responsiveness	Technical foundations	Integrated supply chain and firm performance
Close external relationship	.533			
Organisational flexibility	.661			
Customer delight	.575			
Enhancing performance	.571			
Ethics and integrity	.589			
People strategy	.722			
Innovation	.663			
Integrating internal operations	.760			
Managing change	.643			
Marketing communication	.614			
Organisational communication	.991			
Organisational decision making	.568			
Pricing tactics		.587		
Market segmentation		.708		
Product design		.693		
Customer orientation		.663		
Targeting different market segments		.700		
People development			.573	
Positioning in customers mindset			.582	
Quality of work life			.618	
Reliable systems			.691	
Service access			.627	
Strategic location			.599	
Technological know-how			.688	
Collaborating partners in supply chain				.508
Financial stability				.796
Global presence				.557
Explained variation	23.10	16.51	15.87	7.30
Standardised Cronbach's Alpha	.936	.889	.883	.621

Table 6: Differences in competency levels by the field of specialisation

	Perceived gap Mean (SD)							F	Sig.
	Finance	IT	Marketing	HR & Administration	Legal	Planning & Corporate Strategy	Operations		
<i>Managerial Competency Clusters:</i>									
Transformational and responsiveness management	-.52 (.57)	-.60 (.51)	-.60 (.55)	-.66 (.64)	-.16 (.59)	-.43 (.55)	-.40 (.87)	.893	.501
Foundational systems	-.46 (.49)	-.48 (.66)	-.75 (.39)	-.96 (.60)	-.41 (.50)	-.57 (.42)	-.44 (.79)	2.670	.017*
Proactivity	-.55 (.71)	-.72 (.77)	-.83 (.57)	-.92 (.60)	-.53 (.79)	-.58 (.60)	-.56 (.83)	1.196	.310
Functional efficacy	-.70 (.70)	-.73 (.69)	-.74 (.54)	-1.24 (.56)	-.65 (.68)	-.68 (.54)	-.55 (.74)	3.824	.001**
Technical writing	-.53 (.74)	-.92 (.90)	-.91 (.73)	-.71 (.93)	.00 (1.00)	-.38 (.50)	-.52 (.87)	1.818	.098
<i>Organisational Competency Clusters:</i>									
Responsiveness planning	-1.28 (.86)	-1.75 (.56)	-1.58 (.74)	-1.56 (.69)	-1.35 (.47)	-1.40 (.91)	-1.48 (.83)	.582	.744
Market responsiveness	-1.48 (.99)	-1.81 (.40)	-1.45 (.57)	-1.58 (.80)	-1.36 (.86)	-1.54 (.95)	-1.55 (.96)	.318	.927
Technical foundations	-1.22 (.86)	-1.59 (.51)	-1.28 (.59)	-1.16 (.57)	-1.31 (.44)	-1.38 (.81)	-1.18 (.78)	.734	.623
Integrated supply chain and firm performance	-1.01 (.81)	-1.06 (.70)	-1.03 (.48)	-1.01 (.50)	-.76 (.59)	-1.04 (.72)	-.98 (.69)	.211	.973

Note: * p<0.05; **p<0.01

Table 7. Correlations

		Managerial Competency Clusters					Organisational Competency Clusters			
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4
Managerial Competency Clusters	1. Transformational and responsiveness management	-								
	2. Foundational systems	.012	-							
	3. Proactivity	.025	.051	-						
	4. Functional efficacy	.014	.032	.013	-					
	5. Technical writing	.031	.042	.024	.023	-				
Organisational Competency Clusters	1. Responsiveness planning	.019	.199*	.206*	.063	.125	-			
	2. Market responsiveness	.175*	.063	.368**	.038	.128	.036	-		
	3. Technical foundations	.032	.032	.082	.231**	.110	.042	.029	-	
	4. Integrated supply chain and firm performance	.048	.252**	.005	.064	.255*	.062	.043	.028	-

Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Table 8: Summarised results- regression analysis

Managerial Competency Clusters	Organisational Competency Clusters			
	Responsiveness planning	Market responsiveness	Technical foundations	Integrated supply chain and firm performance
Transformational and responsiveness management	.050	.219*	.061	.018
Foundational systems	.199*	.104	.025	.236*
Proactivity	.211*	.409***	.074	.011
Functional efficacy	.024	.017	.237*	.090
Technical writing	.092	.158	.130	.238*
R ² (adjusted)	.054*	.178***	.052	.084*

Note: * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Figures

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Figure 2. Relationship between managerial and organisational-level competency clusters

Note: Statistically significant relationships are shown.